

The Influence of Glass-Ceiling Effect and Gender Discrimination on Women's Career Advancement in Educational Sector of Pakistan: Moderating Role of Power Distance

Dr. Adeeba Khan¹, Dr. Saba Ahmad², Dr. Naveed³

¹Assistant professor, The University of Poonch, Rawalakot

²Assistant Professor, Fatima Jinnah Woman University, Rawalpindi.

³Associate professor, Qurtuba University of Science and Information Technology, Peshawar.

Naveed@qurtuba.edu.pk

Received: 06th October 2021

Revised: 19th November 2021

Accepted: 06th December 2021

Abstract: Underdeveloped nations are focused on entering the list of developed nations. To do this, they try to meet the criteria. Education and academia are the focus of attention for many countries, and Pakistan is one of them. In this study, the authors examined those hidden factors that create hurdles and reduce the backbone of academia. Employees, either male or female, play an essential role in the productivity and performance of firms. Unfortunately, because of traditional schools of thought and the strong influence of culture in Pakistan, women face a variety of barriers in the workplace. The study highlights those gaps and checks the impact of glass ceilings as well as gender discrimination on women's careers in the educational sector of Pakistan and the State of Azad Jammu & Kashmir. This study is critical in determining why it plays a crucial role in how women do not reach the advancement level when put side-by-side with male employees. Furthermore, high power distance culture is viewed as a moderator that has a negative impact on glass ceilings and women's career advancement. Data was collected from 355 female employees in middle and upper-level positions. The result has been analyzed by a structural equation model with the help of AMOS. The study's finding support existing literature demonstrating how high power distance mitigates the negative effects of glass ceilings, gender discrimination, and women's careers in the educational sector.

Key words: Glass Ceiling effect, Gender discrimination, Power distance and women's career advancement.

Introduction

Now-a-days half of the world's population comprises of women. In any competitive economy, women have evolved to contribute half of the human capital (Fathy & Youssif, 2020). It is almost impossible to eliminate gender parity because in this competitive environment the one essential resource of any organization is its female employees. Female employees are positively contributed in an organizational performance considering their skill and abilities (Glass & Cook, 2016). In some societies, higher-level positions of

women are normally discouraged due to the influence of various social, cultural, ethical or religious norms, these norms create barriers in women carriers in terms of transparent glass, and this concept is generally known as glass ceiling effect. That hinders the women to research at top level position (Baumgartner & Schneider, 2010). Especially, in Asian countries, glass ceiling like gender discrimination is very high concerning almost every aspect of life, from economic development to climate and terrain to cultural norms and practices (Mohammadkhani & Gholamzadeh, 2016). From all over the world, women are progressively establishing a continuous gender-equality movement to achieve their equal rights and opportunities depending upon their talent and capabilities instead, of gender discrimination (Ganiyu, Oluwafemi, Ademola & I. Olatunji, 2018). But unfortunately in underdeveloped nations like Pakistan still face these thwart and stop women career growth. The challenges faced by women leaders are also diverse and complex. According to the International Labor Organization (ILO) survey conducted in 2019, in Pakistan, only 29.57% of females work in different sectors (public/private) as compared to male laborers (The World Bank, 2019). A very less part of women works in the organized services sector, whereas, the majority is employed in unorganized sectors such as farms, and textile industry etc. Normally, in Pakistan, a women are traditionally or forcibly bound to perform the dual job at home and workplace; therefore, most of the women prefer to adopt low-level jobs with less income (Soomro, Syeda ,Shaikh & dayo, 2020). These women are more creative and competent but due to different challenges they prefer to be quite and do the traditional jobs. Indeed, the distressingly high rate of female infanticide in Asian countries, such as Pakistan, sends a strong signal about how females are devalued in these societies (Abbas. Q, Hameed. A, & Waheed.A, 2010). Moreover, in these societies there are some prevalent gendered stereotypes at the workplace that hinders the recognition of women for managerial or leadership positions. Similarly, in different industries, women make up half of the workforce but they make a small fraction of leadership positions. Gender disparity or the glass ceiling arises when there are vacancies made only for men or when organizations are highly precise about the gender for a given employment role. The hiring procedure takes into account the cultural attitudes. The male dominating organizations or those having masculine culture they probably choose male candidates over female candidates (Pange, Smitha, & Sathiyaseelan, 2020). If the glass ceiling starts at the bottom, it can ascend and twain the ladder all the way to the top. The severity and breadth of the glass ceiling, on the other hand, differ from company to company and sector to sector. A glass ceiling can occur in two ways - one is when an organization does not give ample opportunities for women to growing on their career ladder. The second type is self-imposed, in which a woman decides to stay where she is because of her profession or other aspects of her life (Soumya& Sathiyaseelan, 2021). The current research study highlights this issue and considers that how glass ceiling as well as gender discrimination resist women career growth in Pakistan. There are various factors that influences glass ceiling, but regardless of those factors, glass ceiling disturbs a person when one goes through it. A woman employee when faced with such experiences gets emotionally disturbed and mentally imbalanced not knowing whom to go to or how to deal with such issues that reduces their chances to get growth in their career. Women employees can contribute positively to organizations owing to their skills and attitudes (Glass & Cook, 2016). But due to glass ceiling effect their growth regarding career become stop and they face hurdles to get advance positions at workplace. The metaphor of glass ceiling refers to discriminatory processes that obstruct the advancement of women to higher posts in an organization (Bendl & Schmidt, 2010). Various studies explain the reasons for the glass ceiling, including gender discrimination and lack of social norms (Cook & Glass, 201 4). Previous studies demonstrated that glass ceiling effect positively

associated with higher turnover intention and lack of organizational commitment (Bhatnagar, 2012; Poon, 2013; Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi, 2014). Glass ceiling are hidden barriers or unseen obstacles that female employees face to get top positions on the basis of their skills as compared to male workers.

Therefore, educational sector is back bone of any society, those nations invest on education the raise their standards day by day and show their progress in every field of life. They respect both male and female workforce and without considering gender-discrimination they hire and recruit employees on the basis of their knowledge and skills instead of their gender. Unfortunately, a nation like Pakistan has least concept of competent and skill recruitment and selection of employees. Females in every field especially in educational sector face some unseen barrier in their way of career. These barriers hinders their career advancement and unable them to attain top positions at workplace. Very few studies have been carried out in educational sector of Pakistan and state of Azad Jammu and Kashmir on glass ceiling effect , gender discrimination and women career advancement. The current study highlights the gap and adds some interesting aspects on female career advancement in Pakistan. At global level females are considered as most important assets of any organization. One of the published report demonstrated that 29% of women held positions in senior managerial roles around the world. There are numerous barriers have been discussed on women career advancement like low participation in leadership, networking (Gran, Thornton, 2019) but still there are least studies that has been discussed that unseen effects like glass-ceiling negatively impact on women career advancement. Prior studies investigated that the "glass ceiling" prevents women from advancing their careers and moving into leadership positions (Huang et al., 2019). Women face different challenges in their personal life and same at workplace so, they unable to see these hidden glass walls that protect them to get better positions at workplace (Sandberg, 2013).

By considering previous literature that how these invisible barriers take place and how gender discrimination significantly hinders the growth of bodies. Studies identified that national and organizational culture influences these barriers and boost them to stop positive growth of women an any sector. According to Hofstede, 2021, people in societies with a high level of power distance accept a hierarchical system in which everyone has a place and no more reason is required. They will follow the orders of their supervisors and leaders. On the other hand people in low-power-distance cultures attempt to equalize power distribution and demand reason for power imbalances. Thus Pakistan with high power distance, support the male dominant society and creates the gender discrimination as well as positively influences the glass ceiling effect. Thus current research study takes power distance as a potential moderating variable that has been less discussed in existing research in this scenario. In social science research the gender inequality that leads to glass-ceiling is due to strong male dominant working environment (Sharma & Kaur, 2019). The consequence of male dominance in these societies is that many females are restricted to suppress their talent, capabilities and to participate forcibly in various aspects of life especially in under develop nations like Pakistan. The previous findings show a moderately negative association between the glass ceiling and women's career development, as well as evidence that cultural aspects have a substantial impact on women's career advancement (Fapohunda , 2018). Similarly, the distribution of high power distance externally caused disparities among individuals and deflects the negative effects of inequality in people's shared meaning system (Lopez Reyes, 2018). There is a dearth of knowledge that high power moderate in the relationship between glass- ceiling effects and women career advancement in Pakistan. The current research study fulfills this gap and considers this domain as a suitable moderator of the current framework.

Hypothesis development/ literature Review

Glass-ceiling effect and women career advancement

On comparison of upper level performance of women workers are quite better than the last 30 years but still socio psychological barriers are there that hinders the performance of female employees at job. These barriers are in the shape of glass ceiling and lack of access to training and career development (Sabharwal, 2015; Wilson, 2014). The concept of "Glass Ceiling" was introduced by Ann Morison in the 1980s. It is like an unseen curtain that overshadows the women talent, skills and averts them to hold upper-level positions. Studies demonstrated that "glass ceiling" is the presence invisible barriers, such as unconscious bias, male-dominated leadership, and structural barriers, that hinder individuals from achieving professional advancement (Hewlett, Perraino, Sherbin, Sumberg, 2011; Patton et al., 2017). Glass ceiling effect badly treats the women career advancement. More specifically, women of Pakistan still face these invisible barriers at middle and high level in front of their career growth and women have been underrepresented in top level positions. The concept of glass ceiling by Wall street Journal 1980, determined that glass ceiling is a see-through ceiling that hinders minorities and women to reach at top level position.

These failures to not reach the career advancement level due to lack of diversity in leadership position (Ayyala, Skarupski, Bodurtha, 2019). Some scholars noted that the participation of women is less than men participants in public sector organizations. Women still experience less social contacts than male workforce. Thus, the lack of social contacts and social capital will limit to women career success. It is quite tough for women to get career success and motivation to increase career advancement (Choi, 2018). Those women who face invisible barrier in term of glass ceiling might get fewer opportunities to promotion inside the organization. Moreover, to attain higher position at the workplace women acquire hard work, consistency and belief in them. But due to various barriers, it becomes unlikely, and the glass ceiling (GC) is one of them. Until the early twentieth century, very few researches had been conducted on workplace issues in western and eastern cultures. Even though there is a continuous transformation about the role of women in society, they are still recognized as being less suited than men for managerial positions. Hence on the basis of previous statistical analysis we hypothesized as:

H1: Glass ceiling effect is negatively related with women career advancement in education sector of Pakistan and state of AJK.

Gender Discrimination and women career advancement

The gender gap in academia has been extensively researched, and women's marginalization in universities and research centers, particularly in senior positions, is well-documented. Gender discrimination creates a barrier to career advancement and less workforce retention especially for females at the workplace. Social science researchers examined that career advancement is achieving a top position in various disciplines by passing different stages (Bal et al., 2013). Research scholars demonstrated that due to traditional roles of women they are less promoted (Segovia-Pe' rez et al., 2019), most of the women having families and give more time to them (Costa et al., 2017). In Asian context most of the women face problems in their career advancement due to high level of gender discrimination. It depends upon the type of career women choose and chances of their promotions according to the job nature (Saadin et al., 2016).

Remington and Kitterlin-Lynch, (2018) describes that gender discrimination leads to less chances of career advancement not only in under developed nations but also found in some advanced countries like US.

They concluded that those organization having these barriers they will resist female to be promoted on the basis of their competencies. Prior studies (Carvalho et al., 2019; Fapohunda, 2018), revealed that higher level of discrimination on gender negatively related to women career advancement. Even the highest level of barriers has been found in one of the respectable field of society that is female physicians; they face discrimination in compensation packages that violates the professionalisms and female face higher level of scrutiny than male candidates. Also examined that gender discrepancies in promotion rate seems to be a wide gap in leadership. One of the past study indicate that the rate of initial promotion as an Assistant professor at university level for female is 31% and 37% for male candidates (Lautenberger , Raezer , Bunton, 2015) . Thus we hypothesized as:

H2: Gender discrimination is negatively related with women career advancement in education sector of Pakistan and state of AJK

Power distance as Moderator

Culture is a collective programming of mind. One of the most essential dimensions of culture is power distance. It is the degree to which the less powerful people of a community accept and expect that power is unequally distributed. People in societies with a high level of power distance accept a hierarchical system in which everyone has a place and no more reason is required. People in low-power-distance cultures attempt to equalize power distribution and demand reason for power imbalances"(Hofstede, 2021). Power distance is an individual-level variation in culture value relating to status, authority, (cf. Loi et al., 2012). The large power distance countries like Pakistan , inequalities are expected and desire in terms of gender discrimination and transparent barriers glass-ceiling. Despite of this, power distance is a potential moderator of the effects of inequality and status perceptions on attributions to the extent that people incorporate it in their co-variation analysis (Kelley, 1973). Countries with low power distance cultures, most of the time, power is diffused and opportunities are accessible to many sectors as compared to in large power-distance cultures, power structures are unquestioned and opportunities are contained in a few sectors. Similarly, the distribution of high power distance externally caused disparities among individuals and deflects the negative effects of inequality in people's shared meaning system (Lopez Reyes, 2018).

Moreover, power distance as an important cultural dimension for gender gap that shows how people in different societies view and handle human's inequality. Most of the time inequality takes place in the areas such as un-equal distribution of wealth and power on the other side some societies have elaborated formal systems of dominance; others go great lengths to de-emphasize dominance." (Hofstede, 2001: p. 79). A report conducted by Human recourse development, 2019, many societies considered the women status but least at workplace. That develops such norms, by reducing the existence of female at workplace and prefers bros that established the jobs for bros instead of females. In order to measure the gender gap, in social science research, the data base from world Economic forum, The Global Gender Gap Index, examines the gap in four major areas and education is one of them. From all continents Asian countries lead a highest gender gap and showed that 5% gap in educational attainment throughout the world. The reason of higher gender gap is due to unequal distribution of power at workplace in underdeveloped nations. Prior studies found that countries with high power distance are more concerned about the authority and sometimes they misuse the authority and promotes the male candidates on top and middle level administration position that find power imbalance at hierarchal level (Li and Sun 2015; Umer, R. et. al., 2020), to that extent that may even believe the greater level of gender discrimination and some transparent invisible barriers like glass ceiling effect.

Moreover, culture is considered as some deep rooted value systems of some specific group of people or society. High power countries have multiple level of hierarchies and control mechanism system (Reiche et al., 2012; Hofstede, 1980; Hofstede et al., 2010; Ullah, O. and Naveed, 2021) and the member of organization fulfill the orders without asking any questions. Recent past studies identified that women primed with high power is significantly and positively related with lower level of gender identifications (Vial and Naper, 2016). It means that high power distance culture will give women less chance to ask questions and follow the orders from their bosses and no more chance to show their skills and competencies. Organization with such type of dominant culture mostly creates invisible barriers like in the advancement of career that may be glass ceiling effects and inequalities in gender. High power distance culture promotes the concept of glass ceiling and high level gender discrimination that reduces the chances of career growth. Therefore, in current study power distance act as a potential moderator in the relationship among glass-ceiling effect, gender discrimination and career advancement of women in Pakistan.

H3: High power distance moderates in the relationship between glass ceiling effect and career advancement of women in educational sector of Pakistan

H4: High power distance moderates in the relationship between Gender discrimination effect and career advancement of women in educational sector of Pakistan.

Theoretical Framework

Methodology

Research Design

To test the hypothesis, we collected the data from women employees in educational sector of Pakistan. In social science research good research design is used to increase the effectiveness of the study. There are two important designs that is qualitative and quantitative research (Wiersma & Jurs, 2005). Indeed, De Vaus, (2001), quantitative research design is most reliable and valuable thus current study consider quantitative mode of design for the study. To collect the appropriate data, this research study consider the time lag survey design in which data has been collected in three time lags that contained a time lag of three weeks. The reason to conduct time lag design in current study is to avoid the reverse causality.

Sampling and Procedure to collect data

The survey was written in professional English language and the main author of the study fill the questionnaire one by one by clearing each item concept to the desired respondents. In each round, the surveys were accompanied by a cover letter stating that the research had been ethically approved and also

that people who participated could expect complete confidentiality. The cover letters specifically stated that no personally identified information would ever be released, that only aggregate summary data would be made available outside of the research team, and they could withdraw from the study at any point of time. The surveys also underscored that there were no correct or incorrect responses, it was normal for participants to vary in their responses, and it was important to answer questions as honestly as possible. These specifications help reduce the likelihood of acquiescence and social desirability biases (Spector 2006). Moreover the unit of analysis for data collection is employees not managers instead of leaders This study used quantitative research methods that where the total of 400 sets of self-administered questionnaires were distributed to women administrative and executive staff who work in public and private colleges and universities of Rawalpindi, Islamabad and state of Azad Jammu and Kashmir. In the current research study women as prior sample of our interest. Female of middle level academia were considered as a part of sample including teaching and non-teaching staff. In this study researcher excluded the junior's women staff because they do not have much experience of promotion and might not able to dream about promotion in workplace. Academia was selected because educational sector are the second largest contributor to Pakistan economy and the literacy rate of women is much better than male candidates. The self-administered questionnaires are distributed with convenience and purposive sampling method. In the first time lag data was collected on demographic variables like Age, Gender, qualification, marital status and tenure on specific organization, glass ceiling effect and gender discrimination of women in educational sector from Rawalpindi, Islamabad and state of AJ&K, in the second time lag data was collected for high power distance from same respondents and after the same time interval data has been assessed for women career advancement in education sector. Before distributing the questionnaires specific coding has been done on each questionnaire that after completing first time lag data should be collected to the same respondents in each interval of time. Out of 400, 45 questionnaires were not completely filled and some of the respondent fill first and third time lag so better to discarded instead of half filled questionnaires and authors retained 355 filled questionnaires for statistical analysis.

Measurements:

The questionnaires will be adopted to gather quantitative data for study. To essay to understand respondent's simple language will be used. The desired population will be middle and high-level female employees so; there is no need to translate the questionnaires into a native language. The scales used to measure the four focal constructs were validated by previous research. Each scale was measured by using 5-point likert scale that should be considered as more reliable and frequently used scale in social science research.

Glass Ceiling Effect

The questionnaire for the glass ceiling effect is adopted from the last part by Luzzo and Mc Whirter (2001). By using this we will ask respondents to which degree they agree with the probability of facing nine different work-related barriers in their future career along with a 5-point Likert scale from strongly disagree to agree. The statements included both workplaces situations and potential personal concerns.

Gender Discrimination

The questionnaire on gender discrimination is adopted by UNDP (1993,p,91) 9-items scale .the Cronbach's alpha was .87. The items ranged from 1-SDA to 5 -strongly agree

Power Distance

We will gather the data for power distance by using the 5-items scale developed by Hofstede, (2001) with an alpha value of .75. The items range from 1-strongly disagree and 5-strongly agree.

Women Career Advancement

WAMS instrument covers the items of attitude towards women career advancement. The Turkish version of WAMS is comprised of 20-items which is developed by (Peters, 1974), 10 items related to gender stereotype and the other 5-items are relevant to women career advancement. The 5 point Likert type format is followed and the Cronbach's alpha was 0.8.

Control variables.

The current study included five control variables, **Age** (1=20-30yrs,2=31-40yrs,3=41-50yrs,4=above50yrs) **Gender** (1=male,2=female) **qualification** (1=bachelor,2=Masters,3=M-phill,4=PhD),**marital-status** (1=unmarried, 2=married) **and Tenure** (1=1-5yrs,2=6-10yrs,3=11-20yrs,4=above 20 yrs).

Results and findings

In the current research study data analyzed by considering different statistical test also before statistical test it is better to check the reliability of instrument. Sample size of our study was 455 women employees from different universities and colleges of Islamabad, Rawalpindi and state of AJ&K. To test the consistency of the data, data was collected by distributing questionnaires to respondent after receiving data by using Spss.21. Reliability of scale boosts the researcher confident that the instrument is reliable and used for statistical test further. The scales reliabilities are as follows and are denoted by Cronbach's alpha. Glass ceiling effect with 9 items scale range from strongly disagree to strongly agree the alpha value was .98, gender discrimination with 9 items having .88 , power distance of 5 of items scale were .75 and career advancement 20 items scale were .95 respectively.

Moreover, after checking the internal consistency of data through self-administrative questionnaire, authors checked the validity of selected instruments. To check the structure and validity of data factor analysis has been conducted by considering confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). During CFA few items have low loadings and not load on its own variables. Career advancement 3 items Q18, Q14 and Q9 had to remove due to lack of loading on its own factor. The fitness of model has been evaluated through measurements like root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA), incremental fit index (IFI), Tucker-Lewis coefficient (TLI) and comparative fit index (CFI). Current research paper comprised of four research variables including two independent, one dependent and one moderating variables.

	Chi-Square	df	CMIN/Df	RMSEA	IFI	TLI	CFI
Initial model	2661.787	1565	1.618	0.050	0.912	0.884	0.901
Modified model	2455.554	1560	1.599	0.047	0.881	0.899	0.876

The above table demonstrated different values of initial model by fulfilling then criteria like RMSEA .050, IFI .912, TLI.884 and CFI .901. Although to get the goodness of model fit some modifications had been occurred and by receiving few chances get new values. All of the modified values meet the threshold requirement and boost the validity of model for hypotheses test (Hair, Ringle & Sarstedt, 2013). After running the model, RMSEA =.047 which is less than .05 that identified the fitness of model, IFI=.881, TLI=.89 as well as CFI=.8 all of these measurement values meet the threshold values that determined the fitness of model for hypothesis testing.

Correlation Analysis

The below given table represent the correlation of all research variables. Correlation identified the association between variables. In this study Pearson correlation was used to check the association between variables that should lie between $r = +1$ to -1 .

T2= correlation Analysis

Sr#	Variables	GCE	GD	PD	WCA
1	GCE	1			
1	GD	.072*	1		
3	PD	.668**	.244*	1	
4	WCA	-.045*	-.445*	.733**	1

$P^{**} < .05, P^* < .01$, GCE= Glass ceiling effect, GD=Gender Discrimination, PD = Power distance and WCA= Women career advancement

The above table determined the positive and significant correlation between glass ceiling effect and gender discrimination ($r=.072, p < .01$). There was a significant positive correlation between glass ceiling and culture like power distance with values ($r=.668, p<.05$). Current data identified the negative but significant correlation between glass ceiling effect and women career advancement ($r=-.045, p<.01$). Gender discrimination and power distance are positively as well as significantly correlated with each other ($r=.244, p<.05$) and negatively but significantly correlated with women career ($r=-.445, r<.01$). Thus, result showed positive and significant correlation between power distance and women career advancement ($r=.733, p<.05$).

Hypothesis Testing

H1: Glass ceiling effect is negatively related with women career advancement

H2: Gender discrimination is negatively related with women career advancement.

T3: Un-standardized co-efficient for Structural Path

Structural Path	β	S.E	P-Vlaue
GCE \longrightarrow WCA	-.34	.093	.001
GD \longrightarrow WCA	-.48	.006	.003

The Influence of Glass-Ceiling Effect and Gender Discrimination on Women's Career Advancement in Educational Sector of Pakistan: Moderating Role of Power Distance

*** = $p < .001$, β = (Un-standardized Beta), SE = standard error

The above table exemplified that glass ceiling effect is significantly and positively related with women career advancement ($\beta = -.34$, $p = .001$). The statistical results showed that greater the women employees in public and private academic sector face glass ceiling the less will be their chances of growth in their career thus the hypothesis 1 has been accepted. Similarly, gender discrimination negatively impact on women career growth ($\beta = -.48$, $p = .003$), these statistical results cleared that men & women discrimination at workplace reduces the chances of women employees growth.

Moderation Analysis

H3: Power distance (culture) moderates the relationship between glass ceiling effect and women career. The greater the power distance the negativity between glass ceiling and women career advancement increase

Structural path	Co-efficient	P-value
GCE \longrightarrow PD	.45	P<.05
PD \longrightarrow WCA	-.33	P<.001
Iterm_Term1 (GCEX PD)	.49	P<.05

Previous theory and literature examined that countries with high power distance negatively related with women career advancement. The interaction term results ($\beta = .49$, $p = .05$) showed that power distance highly negative impact in the relationship between glass ceiling and women careers, thus H3, is accepted

H4: Power distance (culture) moderates the relationship between gender discrimination effect and women career. The greater the power distance the higher negativity between discrimination and women career advance

Structural path	Co-efficient	P-value
GD \longrightarrow PD	.39	P<.001
PD \longrightarrow WCA	-.33	P<.001
Iterm_Term1 (GD X PD)	.42	P<.05

Previous theory and literature examined that countries with high power distance negatively related with women career advancement. The interaction term results ($\beta = .42$, $p = .05$) showed that power distance highly negative impact in the relationship between gender discrimination and women careers, as a result H4, is accepted.

Discussion

The current study adds to the body of social science literature by looking at the relationship between glass ceiling effects and women's career advancement, taking into account gender discrimination and power distance. Existing research on the effects of the glass ceiling on barriers to women's advancement to senior positions, such as a lack of family-friendly workplace policies (Acker 2006), lower educational qualifications, insufficient management support for work/life programmes, and attitudinal and organizational prejudices (Bomбуwela and De Alwis 2013). Current research study identified that lack of progression on career

growth due to some transparent barriers like glass ceiling and gender discrimination at middle and high level management. Most importantly, women's labor-force participation is lower than men's, implying that women have less favorable access to social capital or resources than men. It is due to some invisible barriers and lack of support of women at top management positions than men. They face exclusion from social networks than men. Because they lack access to social capital, they will be unable to advance to more powerful positions of greater authority (Choi, 2018). Here, current research study reached the same conclusion that women in education sector either private and public still face glass ceiling that might hinder their career advancement that stop them to get top managerial and administrative position in this respectable sector of any society. Also, statistical analysis also approved this by showing the significant result between them. Secondly, not only invisible barriers resist women to reach top level position, higher level of gender discrimination at middle level and top level female workforce face reduce their chances of growth. Existing studies also support this connection that 62.7% female physicians face gender discrimination than male physicians from patients and staff in United States, the condition is much worse in Asian countries (Dave et al., 2020). Although in this present research authors claimed that greater the gender discrimination the low chances of women career growth in educational sector of Pakistan and state of A&P. A contrary review might predict that gender discrimination in different sectors like hospitals, nursing staff has been well documented but still there was an ample room available in educational sector including public and private universities of Pakistan. This study aligned that how gender discrimination faced by faculty members and administrative staff. The current statistical results are aligned with existing body of research that significant difference between male and female educators and found barriers in and severe issues in hospitality education. Most of the women are underrepresented in administrative positions, underpaid and less promoted by ignoring their competencies (Zhong, Blum & Couch, 2018).

Francis (2017) found the similar findings that promotional processes have potential gender biasness even networking, mentoring and other professional help did not support women to be promoted in construction agency. The negative and significant relationship has been found between women career growth gender discrimination because construction is one of the male dominant industry in any society. Moreover, companies internal policies on attitudes of women influences negatively that resist their growth in career (Hermans, et al., 2016) these findings aligned with current statistical result.

Third, organizational culture like high power distance moderates in the relationship between glass-ceiling effect, gender discrimination and women career advancement. The relationship between power distance and glass-ceiling effects identified that greater the power distance the more invisible barriers women face during their job. Individuals with high power distance are more inclined towards inequality (Curtis, Conover, & Chui, 2012), these inequalities boost the invisible barriers in term of glass ceiling even in developed nations like states and Canada (Ng & Sears, 2017). Although, existing literature demonstrated that power distance and gender play an essential role regarding issues related to women at international level. That indicates that women with high power distance will create negative perception about women managers that leads to unequal distribution of status and power (Ramaswami, et al., 2014). These results are aligned with current hypotheses that high power distance strengthens the relationship between glass ceiling, gender discrimination and women career advancement.

Conclusion & Future Direction

The current research study revealed that glass ceiling is negatively related to career enhancement of women work-force. Educational sector should be consider as the back bone of any developed nation, it increase the standard of living and reduce the level of unemployment. Unfortunately, underdeveloped nations like Pakistan still face the issue in this respectable sector. Highest level of gender discrimination in academic and administrative positions at middle level and higher level also boost invisible barriers like glass ceiling that could diminish chances of growth. Female those who are working not in colleges even at higher education institutions like universities both public and private face these issues. Secondly, the negative relationship among all these variables is due to higher level of power distance. As we know that power distance embrace the concept of inequality in both gender, in contemporary study culture with high power distance strengthen the negativity between glass-ceiling effects and women career advancement. Indeed, higher power distance organization faces higher discrimination in gender at middle level as well as higher level that resist women career success. There are few limitations in this study that might be overcome in coming years by other research in this field of study. Not only female gender face invisible barriers in many organizations male also face these issues. In coming research, male glass ceiling effects should be considers. Also we conduct study on contextual basis we should consider other dimensions of culture and used leaders point of few that their employees faces these issues or not. Future research could include different job attitudes like commitment, job involvement as an outcome of glass ceiling and gender discrimination in educational sector.

References

- Abbas, Q., Hameed, A., & Waheed, A. (2010). Gender discrimination & its affect on employee performance/productivity. *Managerial and Entrepreneurial Developments in the Mediterranean Area*.
- Acker, Joan. 2006. "Inequality regimes, gender, class, and race in organizations." *Gender and Society* 20: 441-464.
- Ayyala MS, Skarupski K, Bodurtha JN, et al. Mentorship is not enough: exploring sponsorship and its role in career advancement in academic medicine. *Acad Med* 2019;94:94-100.
- Baumgartner, M. S., & Schneider, D. E. (2010). Perceptions of women in management: A thematic analysis of razing the glass ceiling. *Journal of Career Development*, 37(2), 559-576
- Bendl, R., & Schmidt, A. (2010). From 'glass ceilings' to 'firewalls' - Different metaphors for describing discrimination. *Gender, Work and Organization*, 17, 612-634.
- Bhatnagar, J. (2012). Management of innovation: Role of psychological empowerment, work engagement and turnover intention in the Indian context. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 23, 928-951.
- Bombuwela, Pon M., and De Alwis Chamaru A. 2013. "Effects of glass ceiling on Women career development in private sector organizations - Case of Sri Lanka." *Journal of Competitiveness* 5:3- 19.
- Carvalho, I., Costa, C., Lykke, N. and Torres, A. (2019), "Beyond the glass ceiling: gendering tourism management", *Annals of Tourism Research*, Vol. 75, pp. 79-91.
- Choi, S. (2019). Breaking Through the Glass Ceiling: Social Capital Matters for Women's Career Success?. *International Public Management Journal*, 22(2), 295-320.
- Cook, A., & Glass, C. (2014). Women and top leadership positions: Towards an institutional analysis. *Gender, Work and Organization*, 21, 91-103.

- Costa, C., Bakas, F.E., Breda, Z. and Duraˆ o, M. (2017), "Emotional' female managers: how gendered roles influence tourism management discourse", *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, Vol. 33, pp. 149-156.
- De Vaus, D. A., & de Vaus, D. (2001). *Research design in social research*. Sage Publications.
- Development*, 79(1), 61-67.
- educational and career-related barriers and levels of coping efficacy, *Journal of Counseling and*
- Fapohunda, T. M. (2018). The glass ceiling and women's career advancement. *BVIMSR's Journal of Management Research*, 10(1), 21-30.
- Fathy, E. A., & Youssif, H. A. E. The Impact of Glass Ceiling Beliefs on Women's Subjective Career Success in Tourism and Hospitality Industry: The Moderating Role of Social Support.
- Francis, V. (2017). What influences professional women's career advancement in construction?. *Construction management and economics*, 35(5), 254-275.
- Ganiyu, R. A., Oluwafemi, A., Ademola, A. A., & Olatunji, O. I. (2018). The Glass Ceiling Conundrum: Illusory belief or Barriers that impede Women's Career Advancement in the Workplace. *Journal of evolutionary studies in business*, 3(1), 137-166.
- Ganiyu, R. A., Oluwafemi, A., Ademola, A. A., & Olatunji, O. I. (2018). The Glass Ceiling Conundrum: Illusory belief or Barriers that impede Women's Career Advancement in the Workplace. *Journal of evolutionary studies in business*, 3(1), 137-166.
- Glass, C., & Cook, A. (2016). Leading at the top: Understanding women's challenges above the glass ceiling. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 27, 51-63.
- Grant Thornton (2019). *Women in business: building a blueprint for action*.
- Hair, J. F., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2013). Partial least squares structural equation modeling: Rigorous applications, better results and higher acceptance. *Long range planning*, 46(1-2), 1-12.
- Hermans, M., Newburry, W., Alvarado-Vargas, M. J., Baldo, C. M., Borda, A., Durán-Zurita, E. G., ... & Zwerg-Villegas, A. M. (2017). Attitudes towards women's career advancement in Latin America: The moderating impact of perceived company international proactiveness. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 48(1), 90-112.
- Hewlett SA, Perraino K, Sherbin L, Sumberg K. The sponsor effect: breaking through the last glass ceiling. Harvard Business Review Research Report. Cambridge, Massachusetts: Harvard Business Publishing; 2011.
- Hofstede G. 2001. *Culture's Consequences: Comparing Values, Behaviors, Institutions and Organizations Across Nations*, 2nd ed. (Sage, Thousand Oaks, CA).
- Hofstede G. 2021. Hofstede Insights: National Culture. URL <https://hi.hofstede-insights.com/nationalculture> [Official website]
- Hofstede, G. (2001). *Cultures Consequences* (2nd eds). Thousand Oaks: Sage.
- Hofstede, G., 1980. *Culture's Consequences: International Differences in Work-Related Values*. Sage, Beverly Hills, CA.
- Hofstede, G., Hofstede, G.J., Minkov, M., 2010. *Cultures and Organizations: Software of the Mind*, Revised and Expanded, 3rd ed. McGraw Hill, New York.
- Huang, J., Krivkovich, A., Starikova, I., Yee, L. and Zanoschi, D. (2019). *Women in the Workplace 2019*. McKinsey Report, October 2019. Sandberg, S. (2013). *Lean in: Women, work, and the will to lead*. New York: Knopf

- Lautenberger D, Raezer C, Bunton SA. Analysis in brief: the underrepresentation of women in leadership positions at U.S. medical schools. February 2015.
- Li, Y., and Sun, J.-M. (2015). Traditional Chinese leadership and employee voice behavior: A cross-level examination. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 26, 172–189.
- Loi, R., Lam, L.W. and Chan, K.W. (2012), "Coping with job insecurity: the role of procedural justice, ethical leadership and power distance orientation", *Journal of Business Ethics*, Vol. 108 No. 3, pp. 361-372.
- Lu, D. W., Lall, M. D., Mitzman, J., Heron, S., Pierce, A., Hartman, N. D., ... & Strout, T. D. (2020). #MeToo in EM: a multicenter survey of academic emergency medicine faculty on their experiences with gender discrimination and sexual harassment. *Western Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 21(2), 252.
- Luzzo, D.A. & McWhirter, E.M. (2001), Sex and ethnic differences in the perception of
- Mohammadkhani, F., & Gholamzadeh, D. (2016). The influence of leadership styles on the women's glass ceiling beliefs. *Journal of Advanced Management Science Vol*, 4(4)..
- Mohammadkhani, F., & Gholamzadeh, D. (2016). The influence of leadership styles on the women's glass ceiling beliefs. *Journal of Advanced Management Science Vol*, 4(4).
- Patton EW, Griffith KA, Jones RD, Stewart A, Ubel PA, Jagsi R. Differences in mentor-mentee sponsorship in male vs female recipients of national institutes of health grants. *JAMA Intern Med* 2017;177: 580-2.
- Peters, L. H., Terborg, J.R., & Taylor, J. . (1974). Women as Managers Scale: A measure of attitudes toward women in management positions. JSAS Catalog of Selected Documents in Psychology, Ms. No. 585
- Poon, J. M. (2013). Relationships among perceived career support, affective commitment, and work engagement. *International Journal of Psychology*, 48, 1148–1155.
- Ramaswami, A., Huang, J., Dreher, G. (2014). Interaction of gender, mentoring, and power distance on career attainment: A cross-cultural comparison. *Human Relations*, 67, 153-173.
- Reiche, S.R., Yih-teen, L., Quintanilla, J., 2012. Cultural perspectives on comparative HRM. In: Stahl, G.K., Björkman, I., Morris, S. (Eds.), *Handbook of Research on Comparative Human Resource Management*. Edward Elgar, Cheltenham, pp. 51–68.
- Remington, J. and Kitterlin-Lynch, M. (2018), "Still pounding on the glass ceiling: a study of female leaders in hospitality, travel, and tourism management", *Journal of Human Resources in Hospitality & Tourism*, Vol. 17 No. 1, pp. 22-37.
- Reyes, M. L. (2018). Social mobility attributions in East Asian and Pacific cultures: Power distance and individualism as moderators of self-attribution bias. *Journal of Pacific Rim Psychology*, 12.
- Saadin, I., Ramli, K., Johari, H. and Harin, N.A. (2016), "Women and barriers for upward career advancement – a survey at Perak state secretariat, Ipoh, Perak", *Procedia Economics and Finance*, Vol. 35, pp. 574-581.
- Sabharwal, M. (2015). From glass ceiling to glass cliff: Women in senior executive service. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 25, 399-426.
- Sandberg, S. (2013). *Lean in: Women, work, and the will to lead*. New York: Knopf
- Segovia-Pérez, M., Figueroa-Domecq, C., Fuentes-Moraleda, L. and Muñoz-Mazón, A. (2019), "Incorporating a gender approach in the hospitality industry: female executives' perceptions", *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, Vol. 76, pp. 184-193.

- Seligman, M. E., & Csikszentmihalyi, M. (2014). Positive psychology: An introduction (pp. 279–298). Springer Netherlands.
- Sharma, S., & Kaur, R. (2019). Glass ceiling for women and work engagement: The moderating effect of marital status. *FIIB Business Review*, 8(2), 132-146.
- Soomro, F. A., Syeda, K., Shaikh, S., & Dayo, A. J. (2020). An Empirical Study Of Gender Discrimination And Employee Performance Among Academic Staff Of Government Universities: Evidence From Pakistan.
- Soumya, R. R., & Sathiyaseelan(2020), A. GLASS CEILING EXPERIENCES OF WOMEN MANAGERS- A MENTAL HEALTH PERSPECTIVE. *Journal of critical review*, 7(4), ISSN- 2394-5125.
- Soumya, R. R., & Sathiyaseelan(2020),A glass ceiling experiences of women managers-a mental health perspective. *Journal of critical review*, 7(4), ISSN- 2394-5125.
- Soumya, R. R., & Sathiyaseelan, A. (2021). Mindfulness: An emotional aid to the glass ceiling experiences. *Cogent Psychology*, 8(1), 1907911.
- Spector, P.E. (2006). Method variance in organizational research: Truth or urban legend? *Organizational Research Methods*, 9, 221–232.
- Vial, A. C., & Napier, J. L. (2017). High power mindsets reduce gender identification and benevolent sexism among women (but not men). *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, 68, 162-170.
- Ullah, O. (2021). Effect of Female Directors on Earnings Management in Family Firms in Non-Financial Companies in Pakistan. *City University Research Journal*, 11(2).
- Umer, R., Abbas, N., & Hussain, S. (2020). The Gender Diversity and Earnings Management Practices: Evidence from Pakistan. *City University Research Journal*, 10(2), 342-357.
- Wiersma, W., & Jurs, S.G. (2005). Research methods in education: an introduction (8th Ed.). Boston, Massachusetts. Pearson.
- Wilson, E. (2014). Diversity, culture and the glass ceiling. *Journal of Cultural Diversity*, 21, 83-89.
- Zhong, Y., Blum, S. C., & Couch, S. (2018). Facilitators and constraints: Perceptions of gender differences on women’s career advancement. *Journal of Tourism and Hospitality Management*, 6(2), 61-72.